

D3.5 - Toolkit for implementing tourism crowd visualization analytics solutions

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Executive Summary

This toolkit aims at facilitating the conception of tourism crowding visualization applications, namely by including an online tutorial (video and textual contents) describing configuration and deployment instructions. This kind of application is especially relevant for tourism SMEs that organize events for large groups of tourists where they have to monitor the occupation of the space where it takes place, either to ensure better space management of attendees (e.g., to forward crowds to areas with lower occupancy), for security reasons (e.g., to avoid tampering with exposed objects in a museum space), health reasons (e.g., to avoid exceeding the maximum density of people allowed by health authorities in an event space to prevent contagion in times of pandemic), or simply because of workforce management considerations (e.g., to calculate the expected time for evacuating a concert arena to allow cleaning teams to proceed). This toolkit is agnostic to the crowd detection technology used (e.g. wifi devices detection, infrared cameras, laser detectors), whose crowding measures should be ingested in the chosen timeseries database. The ingestion process is outside the scope of this document.

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Terminology and Acronyms

<i>API</i>	<i>Application Programming Interface</i>
<i>ASGI</i>	<i>Asynchronous Server Gateway Interface</i>
<i>CA</i>	<i>Certificate Authority</i>
<i>CLI</i>	<i>Command Line Interface</i>
<i>CPU</i>	<i>Central Processing Unit</i>
<i>CSV</i>	<i>Comma Separated Values</i>
<i>DBMS</i>	<i>DataBase Management System</i>
<i>DMO</i>	<i>Destination Management Organization</i>
<i>HTTP</i>	<i>HyperText Transfer Protocol</i>
<i>HTTPS</i>	<i>HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure</i>
<i>IaaS</i>	<i>Infrastructure as a Service</i>
<i>JAR</i>	<i>Java Archive</i>
<i>JSON</i>	<i>JavaScript Object Notation</i>
<i>MITM</i>	<i>Man In The Middle</i>
<i>ORM</i>	<i>Object Relational Mapping</i>
<i>OSM</i>	<i>OpenStreetMap</i>
<i>RAM</i>	<i>Random Access Memory</i>
<i>RDBMS</i>	<i>Relational DataBase Management System</i>
<i>REST</i>	<i>Representational State Transfer</i>
<i>SaaS</i>	<i>Software as a Service</i>
<i>SME</i>	<i>Small to Medium Enterprise</i>
<i>SPA</i>	<i>Single Page Application</i>
<i>STEP</i>	<i>Sustainable Tourism Experience or Product</i>
<i>STT</i>	<i>Smart Tourism Tool</i>
<i>STToolkit</i>	<i>Toolkit for building STTs</i>
<i>TCO</i>	<i>Total Cost of Ownership</i>
<i>TLS</i>	<i>Transport Layer Security</i>
<i>UI</i>	<i>User Interface</i>
<i>UML</i>	<i>Unified Modeling Language</i>
<i>URI</i>	<i>Uniform Resource Identifier</i>
<i>URL</i>	<i>Uniform Resource Locator</i>
<i>VPS</i>	<i>Virtual Private Server</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>WSGI</i>	<i>Web Server Gateway Interface</i>
<i>YAML</i>	<i>YAML Ain't Markup Language</i>

1. Introduction

Smart Tourism Tools (STTs) refer to the application of ICT for developing innovative tools and approaches to improve tourism. That improvement may express itself in diverse ways such as by enhancing tourism experiences, improving the efficiency of resource management at a micro and macro level, ensuring that benefits are well distributed and/or maximizing destination competitiveness with an emphasis on sustainable aspects. Summing up, STTs are a key element in improving the quality of tourism services provided by SMEs, boosting their competitiveness, strengthening their sustainability performance, and maintaining Europe's position as a leading tourist destination.

In the scope of Work Package 3, Task 3.3, hereinafter referred as WP3/T3.3, we aim at customizing, productizing, evaluating, and deploying STTs prototypes (products and or services) for facilitating the conception of tourism crowding monitoring applications, namely by including an online tutorial (video and textual contents) for building crowd detectors and installing its driving software (that will be made available on an open-source repository), as well as configuration and deployment instructions. This kind of application is especially relevant for tourism SMEs that organize events for large groups of tourists where they have to monitor the occupation of the space where it takes place, either to ensure better space management of attendees (e.g. to forward crowds to areas with lower occupancy), for security reasons (e.g. to avoid tampering with exposed objects in a museum space), health reasons (e.g. to avoid exceeding the maximum density of people allowed by health authorities in an event space to prevent contagion in times of pandemic), or simply because of workforce management considerations (e.g. to calculate the expected time for evacuating a concert arena to allow cleaning teams to proceed).

This deliverable proposes a toolkit (abbreviated as STToolkit) to scaffold the creation of the aforementioned STTs and is an instantiation of a previous RESETTING deliverable – “D3.3 - *Meta-manual for producing toolkits for STTs*”. Three types of stakeholders are considered, herein referred as **stakeholder roles**:

- **STToolkit Instantiator role** - SME member(s) (or subcontractor) in charge of instantiating / tailoring a given STToolkits to produce a desired Smart Tourism Tool (STTool);
- **STTool Operator role** - representing the SME member(s) in charge of operating the produced STTool (i.e. guaranteeing their availability to users and being able to troubleshoot and overcome failures in operation);
- **STTool User role** - representing the final users of the STTool, i.e. the tourists using it.

2. Deployment Scenarios

Deployment scenarios are business-driven and are inputs for both Technical Planning and Financial Planning. Each deployment scenario should include its location and range (e.g. from a few square meters indoor to wide outdoor areas). For smaller areas, the usage of sensors for obtaining crowding data (using e.g. wifi devices detection, infrared cameras, laser detectors) may be the best solution. For areas with a radius of 100 meters or more, consider contacting mobile network operators to purchase their data, as the cost of deploying and maintaining many sensors may exceed the cost of obtaining mobile operator data. The availability of required technical skills in the SME team is also a critical scenario feature, since their absence may hamper deployment and/or cause cost surplus due to required subcontracting.

We now introduce a set of deployment scenarios for this STToolkit.

2.1. Mass Events in Delimited Spaces Scenario

STAKEHOLDER: Tourism Animation SME that manages the delimited space

As an example of this scenario, consider the context of outdoor music festivals held in expansive public areas like parks. Within this setting, access to the delimited space is controlled. Examining historical crowding data within this environment proves invaluable for delineating effective evacuation plans. By factoring in the varying carrying capacities of different areas, this data aids in strategic capacity planning, ultimately enhancing the overall experience for event attendees. The capability to visualize real-time crowding data in a delimited space enables swift responses to evolving scenarios, particularly contributing to the assurance of attendee security and safety. This proactive approach ensures that organizers can adapt promptly to changing circumstances, fostering an environment that prioritizes the well-being and satisfaction of the crowd.

2.2. Mass Events in Open Public Spaces Scenario

STAKEHOLDER: Tourism Animation SME hired by city authorities to organize the event

In contrast to the previous scenario, the distinguishing feature of this one is the absence of controlled access to the public space, elevating security concerns. The unregulated entry poses a heightened need for effective crowd management. Once more, the capacity to visualize real-time

crowding data proves instrumental in efficiently overseeing the crowd and responding promptly to any emergent situations discernible through data analysis. A practical example is the dynamic deployment of sanitation teams, strategically assigned to clean up areas as they exhibit a decrease in crowd density. This proactive approach ensures not only the maintenance of cleanliness but also contributes to the overall safety and satisfaction of the attendees by addressing potential challenges in real-time.

2.3. Crowded Indoor Scenario

STAKEHOLDER: Museums and other indoor tourism attractions

This scenario relates to the visitation of indoor sites such as museums or palaces. The two main problems in managing highly sought-after destinations with these characteristics are admissions control and internal management of occupancy and flow between the various rooms. Regarding the former, crowding data can help optimize reservation slots, ensuring a steady flow of visitors throughout the day and preventing overcrowding during peak hours. Crowding data can also inform dynamic pricing models. Higher entry fees during peak times can incentivize visitors to choose less crowded times, helping to distribute the flow of tourists more evenly.

2.4. Smart Areas Management Scenario

STAKEHOLDER: Destination Management Organization (DMO)

Year-round access to discrete data is paramount as it facilitates the identification of regional and seasonal patterns, crucial for effective management of sensitive areas like Smart Cities or Natural Parks. These tools empower Destination Management Organizations (DMOs) to monitor critical aspects such as crowd levels in sensitive areas and align them with the designated carrying capacity for optimal management. Additionally, these tools assist in identifying operational locations and time frames, exemplified by applications in sanitation management within Smart Cities. Moreover, they play a pivotal role in uncovering new potential areas and markets that might not have initially been considered as tourism attractions, thereby broadening the scope for strategic planning and development within the tourism industry.

Table 1 summarizes the main characteristics of the suggested usage scenarios for this STToolkit.

Table 1 – Deployment Scenarios Characterization

Scenario Features	Mass Events in Delimited Spaces Scenario	Mass Events in Open Public Spaces Scenario	Crowded Indoor Scenario	Smart Areas Management Scenario
Location	Outdoor	Outdoor	Indoor	Outdoor
Visitation	Intensive within a given time frame, with controlled access	Intensive within a given time frame and with uncontrolled access	Indoor space with controlled access all year round	Wide area public space, all year round
Examples	Large cultural events, e.g. rock festival, archeological site visiting	Political rallies, fireworks, video mapping, Pilgrimage sites.	Museums, historical monument, Tech Summits and Fairs	Local management of crowded historical neighborhoods, Natural/National parks management.
Range	tens of ha	tens of ha	< tens of ha	tens of ha, town, city, village, or neighborhood
Geo-mapping	OpenStreetMap	OpenStreetMap	Custom map	OpenStreetMap, custom maps

3. Toolkit Classification

This section classifies this toolkit according to the STT taxonomy proposed in the RESETTING deliverable “D3.3 - Meta-manual for producing toolkits for STTs”. This same taxonomy will be used to classify the STTs that will populate the European Observatory on Smart Tourism Tools being developed in the context of Task 3.2 of Work Package 3.

The proposed taxonomy has several aspects, described in the following subsections.

3.1. Action Domain and Tool Type

According to the proposed taxonomy, the action domains and corresponding STT types we could identify for this STTool are those detailed in Table 2.

Table 2 – Classification of Action Domain and Tool Type

ACTION DOMAIN	STT TYPE	DESCRIPTION
Management & Operations	Design of tourism products	STT aimed at helping in the creation of touristic offer (e.g., B2B platforms helping build tourism packages)
	Operation of tourism products	STT assists in the operation of touristic offerings (e.g., crowd management tools).
	Maintenance/evolution of tourism products	STT helps in the evaluation and decision-making regarding the existing touristic offer (e.g., data analytics tools).

3.2. Technical Characterization

The technologies required to instantiate this STT are:

- Data Analytics and Visualization
- Cloud computing
- 3D visualization
- Software installation/configuration
- Geographical Information Systems
- Cloud-based time series database

3.3. Required Skills

The STTools based on our toolkit include software that must be installed and configured/tuned before being put into operation. There are three different deployment scenarios: on-premise hosting (private server); third party cloud hosting (IaaS - Infrastructure as a Service); or RESETTING cloud hosting (SaaS - Software as a Service).

Then, when the system is in operation with final users, we should guarantee that it keeps providing its service smoothly without interruptions or service degradation. Therefore, we considered separately the required skills for software in those two phases: installation and maintenance.

Followingly we briefly characterize each of the former two categories and then gauge their required level of skills using a semantic differential scale in Figure 1, where two bipolar adjectives are used at the endpoints: generalist and specialist. Generalist skills are those based on common sense or due to exposure to technologies used in day-to-day life, like using a mobile phone and installing apps on it. Specialized skills are those that require specific technical training (formal or professional) and/or effective hands-on in-depth experience.

3.3.1. On-premise server & IaaS

These two deployment scenarios have a similar set of required skills for installation and maintenance.

- Installation: Follow instructions on how to set up the software on the server, adjust the configuration files in order to integrate the application with the data sources.
- Maintenance: Adjustments to the setup as the dataset and technologies evolve. Troubleshoot availability issues.

3.3.2. RESETTING SaaS

- Installation: Installation is done by RESETTING.
- Maintenance: Maintenance is done by RESETTING. The client must be able to communicate any technical issues they might encounter.

Figure 1 - Required skills for software installation and maintenance regarding 'On-premise server' & 'Third party IaaS' deployment and operation

Figure 2 - Required skills for software installation and maintenance regarding 'RESETTING SaaS' deployment and operation

3.4. Sustainability Focus

This aspect deals with the concern on sustainability matters considered during STT development. We will use here the same sustainability indicators used for STEPs (Sustainable Tourism Experiences and Products) to be developed in the scope of Task 3.6 (Sustainable B2B Marketplace). These indicators are defined along with 3 dimensions:

- **Environmental sustainability.** Environmental performance evaluation considering:
 - Land use;
 - Energy use;
 - Resource extraction;
 - Water use;
 - Pollution of water and soil;
 - GreenHouse gas emissions;
 - Other air pollutant emissions.

- **Social sustainability.** Social performance evaluation mainly focused on understanding:
 - Labor relations/conditions;
 - Relations with the community;
 - Customer relations;
 - Supplier control and fair trade policy;
 - "Edutainment" value.

- **Destination sustainability.** Evaluation of the quality, sensibility, and sustainability of the destination on a regional scale. Qualification of the territory and understanding of the local impact of your STT considering:
 - Environmental quality (resource use, pollution levels, natural status);
 - Socio-cultural authenticity;
 - Level of heritage protection (natural, socio-cultural, and/or built).

The indicator for each of the latter is rated on a **5-point Likert scale** (e.g. Extremely Effective - 5, Very Effective - 4, Moderately Effective - 3, Slightly Effective - 2, Not at all Effective - 1), in response to these questions **for STT's final users (tourists)**, and combined in a Kiviati Diagram (aka Radar Chart), for each of the planned deployment scenarios (Figures 2 through 5), to allow a more concise view and comparability of the sustainability focus provided by the STT.

Figure 3 - Mass Events in Delimited Spaces scenario sustainability indicators

Figure 4 - Mass Events in Open Public Spaces scenario sustainability indicators

Figure 5 - Crowded Indoor Scenario scenario sustainability indicators

Figure 6 - Smart Areas Management scenario sustainability indicators

3.5. Accessibility Focus

This aspect deals with the concern on accessibility matters considered during STT development. In other words, we aim to evaluate if people with disabilities will benefit by using or operating the STT. We will consider two populations: one of final users (i.e., tourists) and another of STT operators, i.e. those who install the STT and ensure its operation/availability. We consider 4 disability/impairment dimensions: vision, hearing, mobility, and cognition.

The indicator for each of the latter will be rated on a **5-point Likert scale** (e.g. Extremely Effective - 5, Very Effective - 4, Moderately Effective - 3, Slightly Effective - 2, Not at all Effective - 1), in response to these questions **for STT's final users (tourists) and STT operators (installation and operation)**:

- How effective is it to allow users with vision disabilities to use it for the intended purpose?
- How effective is it to allow users with hearing disabilities to use it for the intended purpose?

- How effective is it to allow users with mobility disabilities to use it for the intended purpose?
- How effective is it to allow users with cognitive disabilities to use it for the intended purpose?

To allow a more concise view and comparability of the accessibility focus provided by the STT, a double Kiviatt Diagram (aka Radar Chart) is used in Figure 7.

Figure 7 - Tourists and operators accessibility indicators

4. STT System Description

This section describes system components that integrate the STToolkit. All of these components are software components. Tools for obtaining the crowding data are outside of the scope of this STToolkit. One available solution to capture crowding data through Wi-Fi sensors is [RESETTING's STToolkits for Crowd Monitoring](#).

4.1. System Architecture

The architecture of the STToolkit is described in the UML Component Diagram presented in the figure below. The Component Diagram describes the organization of STT components. The latter are conceptual stand-alone design elements that provide or require interfaces to interact with other constructs (aka artifacts) in the STT.

Figure 8 - STToolkit architecture

The visualization platform provided by the STToolkit is a web application with an architecture consisting of a decoupled Frontend and Backend. In addition, the Scripts component consists of a set of scripts to help set up the platform. These components are described as follows:

- **Frontend** - This component is written in [Javascript/React](#). Its main web page works as a Single Page Application (SPA) with various interactive controls in order to visualize and explore the crowding data. This SPA depends on various open-source third party libraries, the most important being a mapping library and a visualization framework that operates atop the aforementioned library. There are also other web pages that serve as a frontend for the access control mechanisms of the platform.
- **Backend** - The backend is written in [Python/Flask](#) and it is responsible for fetching and processing crowding data so it can be visualized in the frontend. It has an extensible, connector-based architecture so it can fetch data from different types of data sources without modifying the existing source code. In addition, the backend implements the logic of the access control mechanisms, for which it is necessary a relational database for storing user credentials.
- **Scripts** - This component consists of standalone configuration scripts that aid the setup of the platform.

4.1.1. Frontend

The frontend is a [Next.js](#) application, although it does not make much use of the backend capabilities of the framework. It is written in Javascript and makes heavy use of React. It uses [MapLibre](#) as its mapping library and [deck.gl](#) as the visualization framework on top of MapLibre's three-dimensional WebGL capabilities. The geographic data is fetched from [OpenStreetMap](#) as raster tiles. Besides the main 3D visualization, there is a line chart component in the SPA, created with the [Chart.js](#) library. [MaterialUI](#) was used for the UI components (widgets), in particular for the slider whose background encodes a temporal visualization through the use of a color gradient. Besides the SPA, the frontend contains multiple pages intended for user authentication and management.

When deploying the platform through the recommended [Docker](#) setup, there should be no need for any configuration. All configuration options are in the backend.

4.1.2. Backend

The backend is written in Python and uses Flask as its REST framework. It is therefore a WSGI application and there should be a WSGI server running it in a production environment. The backend provides three main endpoints for the frontend to fetch data:

- `/metadata` – includes a list of locations defined in GeoJSON, as well as configured options related to available metrics and visualization properties;

- /history – is used to fetch historical crowding data from the configured data source;
- /live – is used to fetch real-time crowding data from the configured data source (this endpoint is not mandatory; it's only instantiated and used when real-time data is available).

In addition to these endpoints, there are others, prefixed by the path `/auth/`, that are used for access control mechanisms.

A [YAML](#) configuration file is read on the backend startup, which includes options related to access control mechanisms, such as [MariaDB](#) credentials. In addition, the configuration file is used to define the data sources from which the three main endpoints fetch their data. There are several connectors available that can be used to define those endpoints. There are connectors for [InfluxDB](#), [MongoDB](#), [OpenDataSoft API](#), [Apache Kafka](#), and a connector to serve static files residing in the file system.

In the future, it is expected that InfluxDB will be required as the data source of crowding data. Support for the other data sources will be maintained through a different architecture, namely through the use of the Scripts component of the STToolkit. This decision has been made in order to remove complexity from the architecture and has the main benefit of empowering all instances of the platform with the same set of features, based on InfluxDB's capabilities.

It is worth pointing out that, according to G2 Grid® Scoring, an independent evaluation following a [well-defined scoring method](#), InfluxDB is currently the [best timeseries database management system](#), as represented in Figure 9. Besides, it is free for self-hosted deployment, which is particularly convenient for an SME.

Figure 9 - G2 Grid® Scoring

4.1.3. Scripts

This component consists of standalone configuration scripts that aid the platform’s configuration. At the time of writing, there are scripts available to fulfill the following goals:

- determine “cap” values for metrics through InfluxDB queries based on quantiles;
- given a GeoJSON with a list of parishes and another GeoJSON with a list of locations, create a JSON with a list of locations for each parish;
- given a GeoJSON list of locations defined as polygons, calculate their carrying capacities;
- given a GeoJSON list of locations defined as points, calculate their carrying capacities by determining their areas of influence on the map.

4.2. Bill of Materials

This bill of materials describes the several choice/trade-off criteria when equivalent options are expected to be found, with a description of different deployment configurations of runtime solutions.

4.2.1. Server

This section describes the bill of materials of the server required to run the STToolkit. Table 3 presents costs of several cloud solutions that can be used to host the server.

Computing Resources:

In the following section it is shown a method for estimating the required computing resources. However, **this method is not totally accurate, and should be considered only as a rule of thumb.** This is due to the fact that the data structures in the backend are dynamic and depend on too many variables that are not practical to account for.

When the server is idle, the containers use less than 0.5 GB of memory in total, according to our measurements. When serving a request that generates a large amount of data, the backend container can require much more memory. We have observed that the required memory is about 2.5 KB per point. We can present this information as a formula that expresses the required memory to serve a single request, so that you can make estimates of required memory for your organization's server based on the expected patterns of usage of the application.

$$\text{Memory of request} = \text{number of metrics} \times \text{number of locations} \times \text{number of moments} \times 2.5\text{KB}$$

Another relevant aspect is the number of concurrent users, which can multiply the required amounts of memory. The number of processors in the server is the maximum number of requests being served at the same time, since the backend is a WSGI application and therefore does not serve requests asynchronously, in contrast with ASGI applications. Therefore you can multiply the result of the formula above by the number of processors in order to obtain a better estimate:

$$\text{Required memory} = \text{Memory of request} \times \text{Number of processors}$$

Server Pricing:

There are several options for hosting the platform's server. One of them is deploying it in an on-premise installation. The other is using a cloud hosting solution, which has a much lower upfront cost in case there is no infrastructure already available for hosting the server. We present the pricing

of a few cloud hosting solutions that can be chosen for hosting the application server. We don't consider some popular solutions from e.g. Amazon or Google as the pricing of these is not fixed and varies according to the actual usage of computing resources. They might end up being cheaper alternatives, but that is not guaranteed.

When considering different solutions it should be taken into account estimates of required memory that can be determined based on the expected usage of the platform according to the formulas that were previously presented. The number of CPUs is also relevant as it gates the number of concurrent requests that can be served. You can have a single CPU serve multiple users, but in that case the loading time is higher as the requests are processed sequentially.

Table 3 – VPS hosting costs for different VPS Providers

VPS Provider	Cloud Server Resources	Hosting Cost (without taxes)	
		Month	Year
Contabo	4 CPU + 6 GB RAM	4,50 €	54,00 €
Kamatera	1 CPU + 1 GB RAM	3,66 €	43.92 €
	4 CPU + 6 GB RAM	27,50€	330,00 €

4.2.2. Client

In order to make use of the visualization capabilities of this STToolkit, a web browser is required. The web application has been tested¹ on Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox and Microsoft Edge. Other modern browsers should work as well. For best results, make sure that your browser is up to date.

The client application is not as resource intensive as the server and it should be fast and responsive even on low end PCs. We measured the RAM usage of Google Chrome when using the application and we determined that it requires approximately 12 bytes per data point loaded, in addition to the idle memory consumption of the browser. The number of data points corresponds to the number of metrics times the number of locations times the number of moments.

4.3. Source Code

All source code developed in the RESETTING project in the context of this STToolkit is available on the following GitHub site: https://github.com/resetting-eu/Crowding_Visualization_STToolkit.

¹ This is for the (recommended) dockerized setup of the server. For the non-dockerized setup the application is only observed to have been functioning in Firefox.

5. Financial Planning

5.1. Total Cost of Ownership

The crowding STToolkit provides guidelines for costs incurred in its instantiation. These guidelines take into account several deployment scenarios and, for each of them, a characterization of which direct and indirect cost dimensions should be considered. It allows stakeholders to produce a financial estimate for their products or services, which is often dubbed **Total Cost of Ownership (TCO)**. Several dimensions are referred to in the literature for the TCO ², such as those represented in Figure 8.

*Figure 10 – Breakdown of TCO into its dimensions
(found in multiple sites; original source could not be identified)*

We have aggregated the previous dimensions in just three, as represented in Table 4, since the prolific dimensions in Figure 10 are only worth considering for large investments, not for a STTool aimed at being used by a tourism SME. Notice that the main conception investment – the “intelligence” provided by its software – is free (open-source), due to the research being developed in the scope of the RESETTING project.

²- See, for instance, “*Total Cost of Ownership*”, 3rd edition, by Gerardus Blokdyk, January 2022, 5STARCOoks, ISBN-13: 978-0655312215

Table 4 – STTool TCO Dimensions

TCO DIMENSION	DESCRIPTION
Setup	Costs incurred in configuring the STTool and making it available to final users (the tourists).
Operation	Costs incurred in guaranteeing STTool's smooth operation (high availability), including user reporting mechanisms, fixing detected bugs, and monitoring the provided service through adequate dashboarding and/or other data analytics approaches to identify improvement opportunities and deploy the corresponding service upgrades. This may include hosting and communication fees.
Training	Costs incurred in training SME members in charge of setting up and operating the STTool.

5.2. Deployment Cost Estimation

The Crowding STToolkit provides guidelines to allow SMEs to assess TCO's dimensions for any of the deployment scenarios, represented in Table 5.

Table 5 – TCO Cost per Dimension

TCO Dimension (€/month)	
Setup (min)	0 €
Operation (min)	3.66 €
Training	0 €
TCO (€/month)	3.66 €

The “Operation” regards the minimum monthly cost for hosting the VPS for the STTool. The “Setup” regards the costs incurred in configuring the STTool; there are no costs in addition to the VPS. The “Training” dimension also has no costs associated.

MANUALS

Table 6 summarizes the manuals created in the scope of this STToolkit, along with the corresponding target roles. These manuals are complemented with video tutorials available on the [RESETTING YouTube channel](#) and textual descriptions (e.g. README files) in the [RESETTING GitHub repository](#).

Table 6 – Manuals included in this document

Name	Target Role	Description
Configuration Manual	STToolkit Instantiator	Guidelines for configuration of the cloud server required for a STT based on this STToolkit
End User's Manual	STToolkit User	Illustrates the user's experience for a STT based on this STToolkit

6. Configuration Manual

This manual includes information about the dockerized setup of the server, a guide to the configuration of the backend component, and information about the scripts that have been developed to assist in that configuration.

As expected, the configuration manual requires readers to have some computer science expertise.

6.1. Dockerized Setup

In the [GitHub repository](#) you can find the Docker Compose configuration file that defines the recommended dockerized setup of the server. The following lists the containers:

- frontend
- backend
- nginx
- memcached
- mariadb (*optional – can be remote*)
- influxdb (*optional – can be remote*)
- mongodb (*optional – can be remote or not used at all*)

We will now detail the containers of the setup.

frontend:

For the build step of the frontend, there is a Dockerfile in the frontend directory from which you can build the image. You can build the image by running `docker compose build frontend`. There are also prebuilt images in [the official Docker Hub repository](#) that you can pull. If you opt for that approach, you need to remove the “build” parameter in the `docker-compose.yml` file and replace it with the following:

```
image: resetting/crowding_visualization_sttoolkit:frontend-latest
```

backend:

As with the frontend, you can choose between building the image using the Dockerfile in the backend directory, by running `docker compose build backend`, and pulling a prebuilt image from [the official Docker Hub repository](#). If you opt for the second approach, you need to remove the “build” parameter in the `docker-compose.yml` file and replace it with the following:

```
image: resetting/crowding_visualization_sttoolkit:backend-latest
```

There is a volume bind configured in the `docker-compose.yml` file, so that the “config” directory in the root of the project is mounted as “/backend/config” in the container’s filesystem. You should place the backend’s configuration file in this directory (instructions for that configuration will be detailed later in this guide). You can also use this directory to place static files that you want the backend to serve, such as the JSON files for the list of locations and for the mapping between locations and parishes.

Note that the image’s command uses a [shell script named “wait-for-it”](#) that is used to ensure that the startup of the backend only happens after MariaDB is ready to serve requests. If you decide to use a MariaDB server in another machine or outside of this docker compose, you need to override the command. You can do this by adding the following line to the `docker-compose.yml`, replacing both `<MARIADB_HOSTNAME>` and `<MARIADB_PORT>` with the correct host name and port of the MariaDB server:

```
command: ["/wait-for-it.sh", "<MARIADB_HOSTNAME>:<MARIADB_PORT>", "--", "uwsgi", "-w", "backend:app", "-s", ":5000"]
```

nginx:

An nginx container is recommended to act as a reverse proxy. This makes it possible to serve both the frontend server and the backend server using the same port so that it is not necessary to configure Cross-Origin Resource Sharing (CORS). The nginx container is also used to provide the HTTPS layer (more information on that in the following paragraphs). In addition, nginx can also be used to provide load balancing in case you want to have multiple backend servers, although such a configuration is beyond the scope of this guide. The nginx configuration file (`nginx.conf`) is in the root of the project and is placed in the container’s file system according to the mount point defined in `docker-compose.yml`. The `ssl` directory in the project is also mounted; this is where cryptographic keys and certificates should be stored.

TLS is used to encrypt data transmitted between the client and the server. This is an important mechanism to protect the confidentiality of your data. In order to use TLS you need a certificate. You can easily create a self-signed certificate, which is **not recommended** since it leaves the communication open to a man-in-the-middle (MITM) attack and therefore does not guarantee confidentiality. The recommended approach is to obtain a certificate issued by a trusted Certificate Authority (CA). Once you have the certificate and its corresponding private key, you should place them on your server's file system, inside the "ssl" directory in the root of the git repository (create the directory if it doesn't exist). The existing nginx.conf file specifies "crowdingVisualization.crt" and "crowdingVisualization.key" as the certificate and private key files respectively. You must either change the names of the files to match the names in the configuration, or alter the configuration to match your files. In the latter case, you'll want to change the lines that begin with "ssl_certificate" and "ssl_certificate_key" so that they point respectively to the certificate file and to the private key file.

memcached:

This container is used to provide the in-memory store for Flask-Limiter, which is used in the backend to implement rate limiting on protected endpoints. No configuration is necessary.

mariadb:

The backend uses MariaDB to store information related to access control. You can use a container for this as defined in docker-compose.yml or you can remove that and use another server. In the latter case, additional configuration is required (see the comments on the **backend** container above). In case you are using the container, it is recommended that you change the environment variables defined in docker-compose.yml so that the root user and the applicational user have secret passwords.

influxdb:

The configuration for this container is commented out by default. In case you want to add an InfluxDB instance to the docker compose setup instead of using a remote instance, uncomment that part of the docker-compose.yml file. You should uncomment both the service and the volume (the latter is near the end of the file). The port 8086 is forwarded by default so that you can connect to InfluxDB's web interface through a browser in order to configure users and buckets.

mongodb:

As with influxdb, the configuration for this container is commented out by default. You can use a remote MongoDB service to serve documents, or even not use a MongoDB instance at all, in case you want to store the necessary files in the file system (as described in the **backend** section above). In case you want to use MongoDB in this docker compose setup, uncomment both the service and the volume at the end of the file. The 27017 port is forwarded by default so that you can connect to it using MongoDB's management software.

6.2. Backend Configuration

Inside the “config” directory in the root of the project there is a [sample configuration YAML file named “config_sample.yaml”](#) from which you can base your own configuration file. In order to increase the understandability of this section of the manual, it is recommended that you have the file open as you read this. Structurally, the file must contain 3 dictionaries: “history”, “metadata” and “auth”. If you want your instance of the application to support real-time streaming, you must configure an additional dictionary, named “live”. This section describes the structure of these dictionaries.

6.2.1. history

This dictionary contains at least two elements: “connector”, which is the name of the connector used for historical data loading, and “parameters”, which is a dictionary containing parameters that are specific for the chosen connector. There are two available connectors that can be used for historical data: “influxdb_history”, which fetches from InfluxDB, and “opendatasoft_history”, which fetches from an OpenDataSoft API.

Table 7 – Connectors and their parameters for historical data

Connector	Parameter name	Parameter description
influxdb_history	url	URL of InfluxDB server
	token	Access token for InfluxDB
	org	InfluxDB organization
	bucket	InfluxDB bucket
	metric_variable	Variable to be used in query that corresponds to available metrics
	location_variable	Variable to be used in query that corresponds to available locations
	filters	List of filters to be added to the query
opendatasoft_history	url	Base URL for HTTP request
	dataset	Dataset to be queried
	timestamp_field	Timestamp field of the response
	location_field	Location field of the response
	metric_fields	List of fields that correspond to metrics

In addition to the “connector” and “parameters” elements, there is an optional element named “derived_metrics”. This is a dictionary whose keys correspond to names of derived metrics and whose values are arithmetic expressions that can make use of metric names. For instance:

```
derived_metrics:
  National: C1 - C2
```

With this configuration, a new metric called “National” will be generated that will be the result of subtracting the value of the metric “C2” from the value of “C1”. For the expressions you can use infix arithmetic operators with the usual precedence rules, as well as parenthesis, metric names, and

numeric literals. Note that you still have to configure the derived metrics in the “metadata” dictionary (see [metadata](#)).

6.2.2. *live*

This dictionary is optional. If present, it must contain two elements: “connector”, which is the name of the connector used for historical data loading, and “parameters”, which is a dictionary containing parameters that are specific for the chosen connector. There are three available connectors that can be used for historical data: “influxdb_live”, which fetches from InfluxDB, “opendatasoft_live”, which fetches from an OpenDataSoft API, and “kafka_live”, which fetches from an Apache Kafka topic.

Table 8 – Connectors and their parameters for live data

Connector	Parameter name	Parameter description
influxdb_live	url	URL of InfluxDB server
	token	Access token for InfluxDB
	org	InfluxDB organization
	bucket	InfluxDB bucket
	metric_variable	Variable to be used in query that corresponds to available metrics
	location_variable	Variable to be used in query that corresponds to available locations
	filters	List of filters to be added to the query
	initial_time_offset	Period of time to be subtracted from current time. It defines how far in the past the connector starts looking for data. It must be specified in "xn" format where x is an integer and n is the time unit ("m" for minute, "h" for hour, "d" for day, "w" for week), e.g. “5m” for 5 minutes
	interval	The expected amount of time to have new data available. It must be specified in the same format as initial_time_offset
opendatasoft_live	url	Base URL for HTTP request
	dataset	Dataset to be queried
	timestamp_field	Timestamp field of the response
	location_field	Location field of the response
	metric_fields	List of fields that correspond to metrics
	initial_time_offset	Period of time to be subtracted from current time. It defines how far in the past the connector starts looking for data. It must be specified in "xn" format where x is an integer and n is the time unit ("m" for minute, "h" for hour, "d" for day, "w" for week), e.g. “5m” for 5 minutes
	max_buffer_size	Maximum number of datetimes that the connector can send back to the frontend
kafka_live	server	The Kafka server from which data is read
	topic	Kafka topic

Derived metrics configurations are also possible for the live dictionary, as described in [history](#).

6.2.3. metadata

This dictionary contains several elements. It contains two dictionaries that must be configured through the use of connectors: “locations” and “parishes”. The first defines how to obtain the points or polygons that define the locations to which the crowding data refer to, using GeoJSON. The second defines how to obtain a mapping between parishes and locations, as a JSON dictionary with the keys corresponding to the parish names and the values to the list of location identifiers.

Table 9 – Connectors and their parameters for locations or parishes

Connector	Parameter name	Parameter description
static	path	Path of the file to be loaded by the connector
mongodb_locations	url	URL for MongoDB connection
	collection	MongoDB collection
influxdb_locations ³	url	URL of InfluxDB server
	token	Access token for InfluxDB
	org	InfluxDB organization
	bucket	InfluxDB bucket
	location_variable	Variable to be used in query that corresponds to available locations
	filters	List of filters to be added to the query
	start	Timestamp of the beginning of the temporal window for the query
	latlong_variable	Variable that indicates which coordinate the value refers to. Values of the variable must be either "latitude" or "longitude"

Another element of the “metadata” dictionary that must be configured is the list of metrics. Only metrics that are in this list will be selectable in the frontend. Each element of the list is a dictionary containing four elements:

Table 10 – Elements for configuration of a metric

Element name	Element description
name	Name of the metric
description	Full description of the metric
shortDescription	Short description of the metric
cap	A value starting from which the maximum of a visual property (e.g. cylinder height or hue) is reached

³ Note that the “influxdb_locations” connector can only be used for “locations” and not for “parishes”

The “cap” value should be a value that is considered to be very high for the metric. There is a script available that can help you arrive at that value. That script will be described later in this guide.

We now list the remaining elements that must be configured in the “metadata” dictionary.

Table 11 – Remaining elements of the metadata configuration

Element name	Element description
locale	Locale of the application (this list of files corresponds to the available locales; the value to put here must be the name of the file minus the extension, e.g. "en", "en-au", etc.)
timezone	Time zone of the application (possible time zones can be viewed here)
initialViewState	Initial state of the map view. It is a dictionary consisting of four elements: "longitude", "latitude", "zoom" and "pitch"
hasDensity	Boolean indicating if the list of locations includes usable area from which to calculate crowding density in terms of carrying capacity
hasLive	Boolean indicating if the application has real time live streaming enabled
columnRadius	The radius of the cylinders in the main three-dimensional visualization

6.2.4. auth

The final dictionary that must be configured is “auth”, related to the access control mechanisms.

Table 12 – Configuration elements of auth dictionary

Element name	Element description
database_uri	URI for MariaDB connection. Note that if you are using the "mariadb" container in docker compose, the hostname should be "mariadb"
initial_user	Email identifier of root user of the application (this is only used in case the users table is empty)
initial_password	Password of root user of the application (this is only used in case the users table is empty)
secret_key	Secret key used for session cookies. Generate with the following CLI command: <code>python -c 'import secrets; print(secrets.token_hex())'</code>
email_sender	Email used to send emails with activation link to new users
email_password	Password for email_sender. In case you are using gmail, refer to this guide to see how to obtain the password (an “App Password” is used, which is not the same as the Google account's password)

limiter	Expression that defines rate limits on protected endpoints for non-authenticated users (see this guide for the expression syntax)
---------	---

6.3. Configuration Scripts

There are several configuration scripts in the “scripts” directory of the project. These are Python scripts that can be useful for the configuration of the application. They enable to fulfill the following goals:

- determine “cap” values for metrics through InfluxDB queries based on quantiles;
- given a GeoJSON with a list of parishes and another GeoJSON with a list of locations, create a JSON with a list of locations for each parish;
- given a GeoJSON list of locations defined as polygons, calculate their carrying capacities;
- given a GeoJSON list of locations defined as points, calculate their carrying capacities by determining their areas of influence on the map.

A useful goal that is not part of these scripts is the ability to import a CSV file into InfluxDB. Refer to [this blog post](#) in order to learn how to use the InfluxDB CLI tool to do that. If you need more flexibility, in case the CLI tool is insufficient, the post also shows how to use InfluxDB client libraries to import data programmatically.

6.3.1. Determine Metrics’ Caps

This script makes use of the “quantile” function of Flux in order to determine metric “cap” values in a systematic manner, through InfluxDB queries.

Before running the script, install its dependencies by running `pip install -r calc_metrics_cap_requirements.txt`. The script is named “`calc_metrics_cap.py`” and takes four positional arguments. Invoke it as `python ./calc_metrics_cap.py config_file start_date end_date <quantile>`.

Table 13 – `calc_metrics_cap.py` positional arguments

Argument	Description
<code>config_file</code>	Path to the backend's configuration file. The script determines caps only for the metrics that are specified in the metadata dictionary (see metadata). The “influxdb_history” connector must also be configured for the history dictionary (see history), so that the script knows how to connect to InfluxDB. The file is only read and not written to; the result of the script is printed to standard output.
<code>start_date</code>	Start timestamp of query in RFC3339 format

end_date	End timestamp of query in RFC3339 format
quantile	(Optional) The quantile that is used in the query. If not specified, 0.9 is used

Even though this script makes the process of determining metrics caps systematic, the quantile choice is still arbitrary. It is recommended that you run the script a few times with different quantile values and check if the values are “high enough” but not “too high”. Using the application itself after configuring the caps with these values is also encouraged so that you can make that assessment.

Note that derived metrics are not handled. This might be changed in a later version of the script.

6.3.2. Assign Locations to Parishes

This script requires two files as input: a GeoJSON of the locations and a GeoJSON of the parishes. The GeoJSON files can be specified either as FeatureCollection objects or as lists of features. The script will output a JSON file as an object whose keys are parish names and whose values are lists of locations identifiers. The script works by checking, for each parish, which locations are contained inside them or intersect with them. The output file can be referenced directly by the backend configuration script, for the “parish” element inside the “metadata” dictionary (see [metadata](#)).

Before running the script, install its dependencies by running `pip install -r parish_locations_requirements.txt`. The script is called “parish_locations.py” and takes 4 positional arguments. Invoke it as `python ./parish_locations.py locations_file parishes_file parish_name_property output_file`.

Table 14 – parish_locations.py positional arguments

Argument	Description
locations_file	Path to the locations GeoJSON file
parishes_file	Path to the parishes GeoJSON file
parish_name_property	Name of the feature property in the parishes GeoJSON file that contains the name of the parish
output_file	Path to the output JSON file

6.3.3. Determine Walkable Areas for Polygonal Locations

The STToolkit can make use of the concept of carrying capacity by displaying the density of crowding relative to a location’s walkable area. In the scenario where the locations are defined by polygons, there is a script that can be used for determining the walkable area of the locations, by subtracting the area of roads, buildings, and bodies of water from the total area of the location.

In order to run the script, you need to follow the following steps:

1. Obtain a binary .osm.pbf file containing OpenStreetMap data for the region that your locations are in. You can obtain such a file at [Geofabrik](#). Note that you can obtain smaller files for specific countries. See, for instance, [the list of files available for European countries](#).

2. Some dependencies of the script are available through conda-forge. You need to have conda installed, which comes in various configurations. We recommend miniconda if you are installing conda for this purpose only, as it is the minimal installation of conda. Follow [the instructions in the official conda documentation](#) in order to install miniconda.
3. Activate conda in a shell according to the instructions of the documentation linked above.
4. Install Osmium by running `conda install conda-forge::osmium-tool`
5. Install the PyPI dependencies: `pip install -r polygon_locations_carrying_capacity_requirements.txt`
6. Have access to a running MongoDB server. To create one locally you can run `docker run -d mongo:7.0.1`
7. Run the script called “`polygon_locations_carrying_capacity.py`”. It takes 4 positional arguments. Invoke it as `python polygon_locations_carrying_capacity.py locations_file pbf_file mongodb_url mongodb_database`

Table 15 – `polygon_locations_carrying_capacity.py` positional arguments

Argument	Description
<code>locations_file</code>	Path to the locations GeoJSON file
<code>pbf_file</code>	Path to the .osm.pbf file
<code>mongodb_url</code>	MongoDB connection URL (in case you are using a local server, it is probably <code>mongodb://localhost:27017</code>)
<code>mongodb_database</code>	Name of the database for MongoDB (you should choose a name that is not already in use)

6.3.4. Determine Walkable Areas for Point Locations

The STToolkit can make use of the concept of carrying capacity by displaying the density of crowding relative to a location’s walkable area. In the scenario where the locations are defined by points, such as in a sensor configuration, it does not make sense to speak of a walkable area. However, it is possible to determine an area of influence around the sensor, which makes it so we can define the walkable area of the location as the walkable area of its area of influence. Our approach is to use isochrones as the areas of influence. We determine the isochrone of a location as a polygon that contains all locations that a pedestrian, walking at an average pace (1.3 meters per second), starting from the position of the sensor, can reach during a defined period of time.

This functionality is actually a pair of scripts. This is because the first script, among other things, shrinks a binary OSM file that is later used to initialize a local [GraphHopper](#) server. That initialization is manual. The second script then uses the server.

In order to run the scripts, you need to follow the following steps:

1. Obtain a binary .osm.pbf file containing OpenStreetMap data for the region that your locations are in. You can obtain such a file at [Geofabrik](#). Note that you can obtain smaller files for specific countries. See, for instance, [the list of files available for European countries](#).
2. Some dependencies of the script are available through conda-forge. You need to have conda installed, which comes in various configurations. We recommend miniconda if you are

installing conda for this purpose only, as it is the minimal installation of conda. Follow [the instructions in the official conda documentation](#) in order to install miniconda.

3. Activate conda in a shell according to the instructions of the documentation linked above.
4. Install Osmium by running `conda install conda-forge::osmium-tool`
5. Install the PyPI dependencies: `pip install -r point_locations_requirements.txt`
6. Have access to a running MongoDB server. To create one locally you can run `docker run -d mongo:7.0.1`
7. run the first script, which is named “point_locations_bounding_box.py” and takes 5 positional arguments. Invoke it as `python ./point_locations_bounding_box.py locations_file pbf_file mongodb_url mongodb_database route_time_limit`.

Table 16 – point_locations_bounding_box.py positional arguments

Argument	Description
locations_file	Path to the locations GeoJSON file
pbf_file	Path to the .osm.pbf file
mongodb_url	MongoDB connection URL (in case you are using a local server, it is probably <code>mongodb://localhost:27017</code>)
mongodb_database	Name of the database for MongoDB (you should choose a name that is not already in use)
route_time_limit	Period of time, in seconds, that is used to determine the isochrones

At the end of the execution of the first script, it prints to standard output the instructions to proceed. They include a link to a JAR of the GraphHopper server, the command to start it up, and the command to execute the next script

8. Download the GraphHopper JAR, available [here](#)
9. Open a new shell, and run on it the command that was printed that starts with “java”, which starts the GraphHopper server
10. Wait for the server initialization to be done, at which point it will output a line containing the following: `org.eclipse.jetty.server.Server - Started`
11. Run the command that was printed that starts with “python”
12. After the script has finished, it will output its result to “point_locations_with_usable_areas.json”
13. You can now close the GraphHopper server by pressing CTRL-C in its shell
14. Copy the output file in step 12 to the config directory of your server so that it can be read by the backend
15. In the backend configuration file, point to the JSON file in the “locations” element of the “metadata” dictionary (see [metadata](#)).
16. In the backend configuration file, set the value of “hasDensity” to true so that the density visualizations are enabled in the frontend

7. End User's Manual

This manual illustrates the experience of an STToolkit end user. It is targeted for the **STToolkit User role**. It includes guidelines for end users (e.g. tourism attraction managers) on how to use STToolkit's crowding visualization web application.

The end user can visualize the crowding information collected at different times and several locations. They can analyze past events using historical data in order to understand trends and better predict future events. It is also possible to use the platform to visualize live (real-time) data, which can aid in short to medium-term decision making.

7.1. Accessing the platform

The platform is accessible through a web browser. Any modern up-to-date browser should work.

It is highly recommended to have the browser window maximized when using the application, so that the visualizations have enough space to present themselves.

7.1.1. *Activating account*

In order to activate the end user's account and define a password, the end user should access the platform via a private URL (address) that is provided by email. After activating the account, the end user can then make use of the visualization component of the platform. The private URL is not necessary after the account activation and the end user can then access the platform through the public URL. Note that the users should not share passwords and/or accounts due to security reasons. If an individual without an account wants to use the platform, they should ask an Administrator for an account.

7.1.2. *Overview of the visualization platform*

After successfully signing in, the end user is presented with a screen similar to the following:

Initially, there is no data ready to be visualized. Before discussing how to load data, let us take a look at the available interface components. Their purpose will be explained in the upcoming subsections.

The component that takes up the most space on the screen is the Map.

On the top left there is a Menu button that can open up the Menu. When you load the application, the Menu is hidden; the screenshot shown above was taken after the user clicked on the Menu button. Clicking the Menu button again hides the Menu. The Menu is a set of toggle buttons that can open Sub Menus. The available Sub Menus, from left to right, are: *History*, *Selection*, *Merics*, *Seek*, *Points*, *Account*.

To the right of the Main Menu button, there is a Slider, and to the right of that, there is the Show Dropdown. There is a component that does not appear in this screenshot, that is the Live Button, used for viewing real-time data. In this case, it does not appear because this instance of the application does not support viewing real-time data. On an instance of the application that supports real-time data, the Live Button appears on the top right of the screen, to the right of the Show Dropdown. On the bottom left of the screen there is a pane that will contain a Line Chart once data is loaded. On the bottom right, above the OpenStreetMap copyright notice, there is a Scale, and above that there is the Coordinates Pane.

7.1.3. Changing password

In order to change your account's password, you need to access the Account Page. To do so, open the Manage Account Sub Menu and click on the Account Page button that appears in the Sub Menu's pane. This will lead you to a page where you can introduce the desired new password.

7.1.4. Recovering account / forgot password

In case you cannot sign in with your account credentials, you can request a revalidation of your account so that you can assign a new password to your account. In order to do that, click on the Forgot Password button on the sign in screen, which will take you to a page in which you should enter the email associated with your account. After clicking on the button, you will receive an email with a new activation link. Follow the link and you will be able to enter a new password for your account. In case you can't find the email in your inbox, don't forget to check emails marked as spam.

In case you received an email containing an activation link but you didn't use the Forgot Password feature, you can simply ignore the email.

7.1.5. Signing out

You can sign out of your account by going to the Account Page, which you can reach through the Manage Account Sub Menu, and then clicking in the Sign Out text button at the top of the page.

7.2. Loading data

7.2.1. Loading historical data

In order to load historical data, you must open the History Sub Menu, a screenshot of which is shown below:

The screenshot shows a 'History' sub-menu with the following fields and controls:

- Start:** A text input field containing '01/06/2022 01:00 AM' and a calendar icon to its right.
- End:** A text input field containing '01/06/2022 04:00 AM' and a calendar icon to its right.
- Interval:** A text input field containing the number '1'.
- Unit:** A dropdown menu currently set to 'Hour'.
- Selected locations only:** A toggle switch that is currently turned off.
- LOAD:** A blue button at the bottom center.

Firstly, you need to define the period of time from which you want to load data. To do that, you should change the values in the "Start" and "End" boxes. When you press the calendar icon on the right of one of the boxes, a graphical mobile-style date selection appears. You can select the year

and month through a calendar widget. Afterwards you can select the hour and then the minute, using a clock widget.

There is another way of defining the Start and End values, without using the calendar and clock graphical components. You can edit the text in the boxes directly by clicking on the date or time and then writing the value with the keyboard. This is a more advanced feature and may cause the selected date and time to be considered invalid. You can always go back and select the value by clicking on the calendar icon on the right of the box, even after you have written an invalid date/time. This method of editing the text directly has some advantages. One is that you can select minutes that are not multiple of five, so that you can select, for instance, 07:03 AM. It is technically possible to select such a minute using the clock graphical component by selecting values in between the ticks of the clock, but you might find it inconvenient. Another advantage of being able to edit the text directly is that you can copy and paste the value of one of the Start and End boxes into the other, so that you then have an easier time selecting dates and times closer to the value in the box you copied from.

Below the Start date and time box, there are the Interval and Unit boxes, which you can use to define the interval that will be used to aggregate and average the data. This can be useful if there is data available for every 5 minutes, for example, but you don't need that level of detail. By choosing to aggregate values for each hour, or for each day, you reduce the number of data points that are loaded, which can increase the understandability of the visualizations, as having hundreds or thousands of points will result in a cluttered interface.

Below the End box there is a switch that, when activated, will make it so that the application only fetches data for the selected locations. This option is useful for loading data only for the zones of interest, which can dramatically reduce the loading time if there are a lot of locations with crowding data. The question of how to select locations will be covered later in this guide.

Once you have configured all of the options in the History Sub Menu to your liking, you can press the blue Load button to start loading the data. The time it takes to load the data depends on various factors, such as the defined period and the number of locations for which it is fetching data. If you find that the load times are too high, consider loading data for a smaller period of time or for a small selection of locations.

7.2.2. Loading live data

Firstly, be aware that the instance of the application that you are using may not have the ability to view real-time data. If it does have that ability, then there is a blue button on the top right of the screen that says "LIVE". Clicking on it makes the application load the most recent data that is available. Besides the most recent moment, it also loads a predefined amount of previous moments to provide context.

Once the data is loaded, you are in Live mode. The thumb (circle) of the slider blinks, changing color from blue to red at a regular interval to indicate that you are viewing the most recent moment. If you drag the slider or use the Seek functionalities to change the moment that you are viewing, the thumb will stop blinking to indicate that you may not be viewing the most recent moment. In this case, the application is not automatically showing the newest data as it arrives, so that you can take

your time looking at older data. In order to go back to having the application automatically show you the newest data available, press the Live Button again.

7.3. Visualizing data

All visualization features that are described in this section are available whether you're looking at historical data or real-time data.

7.3.1. Overview

Once there is data loaded in the application, there will be cylinders superimposed on the map. The height of a cylinder is proportional to the data value for that specific location. That value may be the number of Wi-Fi connections detected by a sensor, for example, or the number of mobile devices detected by a mobile network.

When you hover your mouse cursor on top of a cylinder, a tooltip appears with the numeric value of crowding data for that location.

You can pan the map by clicking and holding the left mouse button on the map and then dragging it. You can change the pitch of the map, or rotate the map, by clicking and holding the right mouse button on the map and then dragging it. You can also change pitch and rotate the map by holding the CTRL keyboard button and then holding the left mouse button and then dragging the cursor, which is useful in case you are using a touchpad rather than a mouse. You can also change the zoom of the map using your mouse wheel, or, for touchpad users, placing two fingers on the touchpad and sliding up or down. When you zoom the map, the cylinders' height changes. This is so that when very zoomed in the cylinders fit the viewport, and when very zoomed out you can still perceive differences in values.

The cylinders of the map show values for a specific date and time. You can find out what date and time is being visualized by hovering your cursor on top of the slider's thumb. In order to navigate through the temporal dimension and visualize different moments in time, you can drag the slider to a different moment. You should be able to see the height of the cylinders adjusting immediately as you drag the slider.

The background of the slider is a color gradient, ranging from green to red. Greener zones represent moments that have overall lower crowding and redder zones represent moments that have overall higher crowding. By overall crowding it means that it considers the data for the whole map at a time, rather than for specific locations. When you select locations (covered later), the color gradient adjusts to represent the relative crowding values for the selected locations only.

On the bottom left of the screen there is a line chart. Its vertical axis represents the sum of crowding values for all locations and its horizontal axis represents time. For each moment that is selectable through the slider there is a corresponding point in the line chart. When hovering a point with the cursor, a tooltip is displayed that shows the date and time, and the crowding value of that point. Just like for the slider color gradient, selecting locations changes the line chart so that it shows the sum of crowding values for selected locations only.

On the top left of the line chart pane there may be a switch that toggles between *Absolute* and *Density*. This is only available for instances of the application that are configured to use carrying capacities of locations. In case the switch is available, setting it to *Absolute* makes it so the line chart displays the sum of values as described above. Setting it to *Density* makes it so it displays density values, that is, the sum of values divided by the walkable area of the selected locations, or of all locations for which there is data if no selection has been made.

On the top right of the screen there is the Show Dropdown. It can have one of three values: *All*, *Selected*, *None*. By default, *All* is selected, which means that cylinders are shown for all locations for which there is crowding data. By choosing *Selected*, only selected locations will show cylinders, therefore reducing the visual clutter and potentially increasing the understandability of the main visualization. If you select *None*, all cylinders are hidden, allowing you to better view the details of the map itself, such as streets and buildings.

7.3.2. Selection

As mentioned previously, you can select areas of interest, which affect both the color gradient of the slider and the line chart. The selection feature is also used by the Show Dropdown, in case you set its value to *Selection*.

There are several ways to select areas of interest, some of which are through the use of the Selection Sub Menu, shown above.

If you click the pencil button, you will enter drawing mode, allowing you to draw a polygon on the map to represent an area of interest. When in drawing mode, click once without dragging the cursor on a position in the map in order to place a point. You can repeat this process multiple times, defining how many points you wish. To close the polygon, double click on the first point you placed or press the Enter key on your keyboard. This will exit drawing mode, and all visualization properties that depend on selected areas are updated immediately.

Another way to select areas of interest is by choosing a parish in the Parish box and then pressing the Select Parish button. You can select more than one parish by repeating that process. Note that there might be no parishes configured for the instance of the application that you are using.

The third way of selecting areas is only available for application instances where locations are specified through polygons rather than points. In this scenario, you can toggle the selection of individual polygons by clicking on them directly on the map.

If you want to reset your selection, you can click on the trash can button in the Selection Sub Menu.

7.3.3. Metrics

We will now look at the functionalities enabled by the Metrics Sub Menu, shown above.

There might be several different metrics in the data set from which the data is loaded into the application. For instance, one metric might account for devices in roaming detected by a mobile operator, while another metric might account for the total number of detected devices, whether they are in roaming or not.

In the Metrics Sub Menu you can map the available metrics to different visual properties of the cylinders on the map, namely their height and their hue. By default, one metric is mapped to the height while no metric is assigned to the hue, and so all cylinders share the same color. You can change this mapping through the dropdown components. When you open the Metrics Sub Menu, only the names of the metrics are shown. These names by themselves can often not be descriptive enough. When you open one of the dropdown components by clicking on it, the names of the metrics are accompanied by their descriptions.

When a metric is selected for the hue, the cylinders take on colors that range from green to red. The level of redness indicates how high the value for that metric is. The line chart becomes a dual axis line chart, with a scale on the left for the height metric and a scale on the right for the hue metric. When hovering a point on the line chart with your cursor, the values for both metrics are displayed. When hovering a cylinder on the map with your cursor, the tooltip that appears shows the values for both the height metric and the hue metric.

If the application that you are using has been configured to take into account the carrying capacity of locations, there is an additional option in the dropdown for the hue that is called *Density*. When this option is selected, the color of the cylinders represent the density of the values for the height metric, expressed as those values divided by the walking area of their respective location. This allows you to have a better perception of crowding, as a location that is a wide open space with many people can have a smaller crowd density than a location with less people but having also less available space for them to be in.

7.3.4. Seek

There are several ways that you can select the moment that is being shown in the main three-dimensional visualization. One of them is by dragging the slider at the top of the screen, as mentioned previously. The other ways are using the buttons in the Seek Sub Menu, shown above.

When you press the play button, the application drags the slider automatically, starting from the oldest moment up to the most recent one. When the application is doing this animation, the play button becomes a stop button which you can press to stop the animation, which enables you to take back manual control over which moment is being shown.

The other two buttons are the fast backward button, in the middle, and the fast forward button, in the right. These buttons drag the slider automatically to the previous or next local maximum, as can be seen in the line chart. This feature may be particularly useful when there is a large number of moments loaded in the application, so that you can more easily navigate through the moments that are potentially more interesting in a crowding context.

7.3.5. *Points*

There is a Sub Menu called Points that is reserved for future use. The feature that has been considered to be located in this Sub Menu is the ability to load data into the application that is potentially more relevant, by automatically identifying periods of time that may have particularly high levels of crowding.

7.3.6. *Account*

This Sub Menu contains a single button. When pressed, it redirects the browser to the account management page. This page allows you to change your account's password and also allows you to log out. Both of these functionalities have been described in an earlier section of this guide.

For administrator accounts, this page has additional functionality related to the management of accounts, which is described in the next section.

7.4. Administrator control panel

When logged in with an administrator account, an additional tab in the account management page is available, shown below:

Email	Name	Is admin	Delete
demo@resetting.eu	demo	<input type="checkbox"/>	
admin@resetting.eu	root	root	

Rows per page: 5 ▾ 1–2 of 2 < >

Administrator [CREATE USER](#)

This page contains a table showing the complete list of activated accounts. The table is paginated, and its pagination controls are shown below the table. By default, only 5 accounts are shown, but you can click on the dropdown component to select a different amount of accounts to be shown simultaneously. To the right of that dropdown, the indices of users currently displayed is shown, as well as the total number of users. To the right of that there are two buttons that can be pressed to move forward or backward through the pages of the table.

The table contains four columns: *Email*, *Name*, *Is admin*, and *Delete*. The email and name of existing accounts cannot be altered. If an individual with an account wishes to use a different email, you should delete their existing account and create a new one with the new email. The root user can grant or remove administrator privileges from accounts by checking or unchecking the checkbox in the *Is admin* column. Regular administrators cannot grant or remove administrator privileges from other accounts – the checkboxes are always disabled for regular administrators. On the last column there are trash can buttons that can be pressed to delete accounts. The root user can delete any account except itself, while administrators can only delete non-administrator accounts.

On the bottom of the page there is a form for creating new accounts. This is the only way to create new accounts. On the text box on the left, the email of the new user should be placed. On the text box to the right, the user name should be placed. Note that both the email and the user name must not be in use by other accounts. The checkbox labeled *Administrator* controls whether the new account is to be an administrator account. Only the root user can create administrator accounts – the checkbox is disabled for regular administrators. Once these fields are set, click on the blue button labeled “CREATE USER” in order to create the user. The user will not show automatically in the list of accounts, as the list shows activated accounts only. Once the user is created, an email is sent to them with an activation link which leads them to a page in which they can define their password, and upon submission of the password the account is considered to be activated and they can login and use the application.